

EXPLORING THE TRANSMISSION MECHANISMS OF FISCAL POLICY IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Fiscal policy plays a critical role in stabilizing the economy, promoting growth, and addressing unemployment and inflation through government spending and taxation. Understanding its transmission channels help policymakers design more effective interventions. This study analyzes the fiscal policy transmission mechanism in Pakistan using time series data from 1972 to 2023, sourced from the World Development Indicators and the Pakistan Economic Survey. It aims to identify fiscal policy channels, examine the link between macroeconomic variables and government spending, and assess the impact of fiscal policy on economic activity. The analysis uses the VAR model, along with impulse response and variance decomposition to understand the dynamic interactions and shocks among variables. The impulse response analysis shows that government spending boosts growth and lowers unemployment in the short term, though the effect fades over time. Tax increases, on the other hand, slow growth and inflation, with mixed impacts on jobs. Overall, spending has a stronger short-term benefit than taxation, but both effects are temporary.

Keywords: Government spending, inflation, tax revenue, unemployment, and GDP per capita growth

INTRODUCTION

A few years ago, economists applied different economic strategies that affected the economy. Fiscal policy is a significant tool to analyze the effect of taxes and government spending decisions on the broader economy. Monetary policy and fiscal policy work with the help of different channels and these channels influence the economy in different ways. Fiscal policy is the policy in which we deal with taxes and spending while monetary policy deals with central banks to enhance the growth in the economy and reduce the inflation through money supply and interest rate. On the other hand, in every country fiscal policy plays a vital role in economic progress. Government spending and taxes are the tools of fiscal policy that have a significant effect on the economy. Governments attain their objectives by influencing taxes and government spending. Fiscal policy uses these tools and reduces inflation, balances economic growth, and resolves the income inequality problem. The main objectives of fiscal policy are economic growth, full employment, income distribution, and stability in prices. With the help of fiscal policy transmission channels governments manage the economy which are the interest rate channel, inflation channel, exchange rate channel, and stock market channel (Ali & Rehman, 2015; Ashiq & Akhlaque, 2019; Safder & Malik, 2020; Audi et al., 2023; ssan, 2023; Iqbal & Nader, 2024).

When the government resources are used then the government plays a significant role in the economy because this policy regulates the government spending and taxes that manage the level of the economy. Through the addition of government spending, taxes, investment, and exports the GDP shows the effect of economic activity. The aggregate demand is influenced by taxes and government spending (Horton & Ganainy, 2022; Marc et al., 2023). In the long run government spending and taxes have a negative impact on inflation and economic growth (Ali & Naeem, 2017; Lupu & Viorica, 2021; Audi & Roussel, 2024; Ahmad et al., 2024). Fiscal policies are more affected due to the dynamic change in the labor market in economic growth. The change in government spending and taxes generates jobs in the market and stimulates financial activities (Rendhal, 2016; Nasir, 2019; Huseyin, 2023; Audi et al., 2024; Zenios, 2024; Shahzad et al., 2025). Furthermore, in the previous study the long time period, the tools

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of fiscal policy have a negative impact on the inflation of goods and services and economic activity, but it has a significant impact in the short-term. The unemployment rate decreases when taxes are declining and government spending increases and this improves the production level (Asandului, 2021; Karishna & Singh, 2020; Marc et al., 2024).

In fiscal year 24, Pakistan's economic growth rate was 2.5% after a decline of 0.6% in fiscal year 23, this improvement is the result of different stabilization efforts but also remember that different challenges have remained here. In May 2023 inflation was expansionary high, 38%, but in June 2024 the inflation was 12.6% decreased. Furthermore, the economic growth was unbalanced with political instability and limitations on exports. The international trade of Pakistan is limited as compared to its neighboring countries because Pakistan buys more products from foreign countries and sells the less products abroad. It means that Pakistan's imports are greater than its exports. In fiscal year 24 the exact figure for unemployment is not given, which is a significant problem. In fiscal 24 government's total budget for 2023-2024 is 14.46 trillion Pakistani rupees as compared to its past year, in this, the increment is 51% which is a huge increment. Pakistan's government's target in the future is to attain 9 to 9.2 trillion rupees of tax which is greater than 21% of the 7.5 trillion targets of the collection of tax revenue. This reason is that governments are more dependent on indirect taxes (Hassan, 2023).

The research on fiscal policy transmission mechanisms is very important to know how government spending and taxes affect economic growth. In this study, the channels examine the effect on inflation, employment, consumption, and investment. Taxes also have positive and negative effects on the economy. The positive side of the taxes is government revenue. With this government invests in education, welfare, hospitals, and infrastructure. The taxes also resolve the income inequality problem. The taxes also have a negative effect on the economy. When taxes are high it leads to a high level of unemployment. High taxes decrease economic growth and investment in business. The reason is that when taxes are increasing, then the people have low money. High government spending increases employment, aggregate demand, and economic growth but it also negatively affects inflation and debt. The previous study examines how fiscal policy affected the Pakistan economy from 1972 to 2023 years. With the help of the VAR model, the Impulse response and Variance decomposition function analyze the fiscal policy transmission mechanism. We use time series data from the World Development Indicators and Pakistan Survey. The Pakistan government gave the Pakistan budget for the fiscal year 2024-2025 which fulfills all conditions of IMF that is tax reforms. In this Pakistan applies 48 percent direct taxes and 35 percent in direct taxes. With the help of this government collect revenue and boost the economy level. In this budget a new tax policy is introduced, that is Late Filers. In this policy, when institutions and people can't pay the taxes on time the government imposes high taxes on them. Due to this people pay taxes on time and increase the tax revenue. This policy is important to make better of financial stability of Pakistan (Hassan, 2023).

This study organized five sections in the following arrangement. Section 2 gives an overview of the relevant literature of the previous study. The data, model specification, and methodology are used in detail, this is used for analyses in Section 3. Section 4 gives the interpretation, and analysis and presents the results of all variables by applying the Vector autoregression (VAR) model, impulse response, and variance decomposition function. Section 5 summarizes the conclusion of the study and contains the policy implications.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of literature is necessary as it provides a substance for understanding existing research, identifying gaps and pointing the direction of new studies. Table 1 shows the summary of the studies on fiscal policy transmission mechanisms.

Table 1: Summary of the Studies on Fiscal Policy Transmission Mechanisms

Reference (s)	Country	Time Period	Methodology	Main Results
Ding et al. (2024)	China	1998-2007	GMM	The result revealed a positive impact of fiscal policy on capital allocation.
Alves & Coelho (2024)	European Countries	1995-2019	SEM	The study concluded that inequality harmed GDP and public income consumption positively affected economic growth.

Apeti et al. (2024)	Developing Countries	1990-2020	Entropy Balancing	The results showed that fiscal rules better maintain foreign debt in developing countries.
Dellas et al. (2024)	Greece	2009-2015	DSGE	The authors analyzed the impact of government spending and tax revenue on GDP, which was positive, but the informal sector had a negative impact.
Woldu (2023)	Sub-Saharan African countries	2000-2018	VAR	The results revealed that fiscal policy positively impacted C and I during the recession and had a negative impact during the boom period.
Hassan (2023)	Pakistan	1979-2022	Least Square SUR	The outcome showed that government spending and taxes had a positive effect, while interest rates had a negative effect on investment.
Ikediashi et al. (2023)	Nigeria	1983-2021	ARDL	The result showed that MPMS, TOGE, and MPOM had a positive impact on GDP but TOPD and CINF hurt GDP.
Ilori et al. (2022)	US & Germany	1990-2019	VAR	The study concluded that public spending had a positive effect on GDP, consumption, and investment.
Hamad et al. (2022)	Iraq	1990-2018	ARDL	The result explored that public spending had an insignificant impact on employment.
Rivero & Guerrero (2022)	Spain	1980-2020	ARDL	The increase in public expenditure and fall in net revenues positively impacted economic growth in both the short and long run.
Ohazurike & Igwe (2022)	Nigeria	1980-2016	OLS	Both government and monetary policies, as well as taxes, had a positive impact on economic growth, while the interest rate was negatively affected.
Bose (2021)	Nigeria	1970-2018	Bayesian	The result showed that macroeconomic variables were affected by public policy channels.
Kamalyan (2021)	United State	1984-2008	DSGE	The results showed that monetary and public policies significantly impact the economy during recession or depression periods.
Submitter et al. (2021)	United State	1986-2017	ARDL	The study investigated the significant correlation between monetary and fiscal policies and the stock market.
Effiong and Okon (2020)	Nigeria	1981-2019	ADF, PP & ECM Test	The study analyzed the fact that monetary and public policy stimulate the economy in the short run, but this had a weak effect in the long term.
Munir & Riaz (2020)	Pakistan	1976-2018	SVAR	Results showed that government spendings positively impact on GDP. Taxes also influence GDP and prices, while fiscal policy boosts the economy.

Brinca et al. (2019)	US economy	1889-2015	Empirical Pattern and Life-Cycle	The observation showed that an increase in government expenditure boosted the economy, while a decrease had a lesser impact, disproportionately affecting those with lower savings.
Agbonkhese & Oligbi (2019)	Nigeria	1986-2017	VECM	The study concluded that increasing money supply and government revenue positively impacted economic growth, while government expenditure hurt GDP.
Shaheen (2019)	UK economy	1987-2017	TVP-VAR	The result showed that government policy had negatively affected private consumption and positively affected labor supply.
Olivero (2019)	United State	1984-2017	SVAR	The outcome analyzed that the cost of borrowing was low due to public expenditure, which had a stronger impact on aggregate output.
Nwaogwugwu (2018)	Nigeria	1970-2016	ARDL	The observation analyzed that public and monetary policies significantly impacted the stock market.
Evans et al. (2018)	Africa	1995-2016	GMM	The result showed that monetary policy strongly affected rather than public policy.
Michal et al. (2017)	European Sovereign countries	2009-2014	FAVAR	The outcome examined that government shocks had a stronger impact on economic output.
Asamoah (2016)	Ghana	1970-2013	Autoregressive Distributed Lags	The study examined that the high interest rate was due to a short-term fiscal deficit and reduced in the long term. The stability of the lending rate also changed with the exchange rate.
Riaz & Munir (2016)	South Asian countries	1990-2014	OLS and Instrumental Variable Least Square	The analysis indicated that while automatic stabilizer and discretionary fiscal policies had a limited impact on the economy, fiscal policy effectively stabilized the economy.
Janssen et al. (2015)	20 Advance economies	2007-2014	PVAR	The study found that during the financial crisis, monetary policy was effective, but it was less effective during non-financial crises.
Fazzari et al. (2015)	US	1967-2012	Threshold Structural Vector Autoregressive	The outcome investigated that government spending had a stronger and more positive impact on GDP, C, and I.
Tafuro (2015)	OECD countries	1980-2009	SVAR	The result indicated that public policy harmed GDP and employment, and an increase in taxes led to a decrease in economic growth.
Daly (2015)	France	1980-2014	Granger's	The results showed that monetary and government policies were poorly coordinated in France.

Ogbulu et al. (2015)	Nigeria	1985-2012	ECM	The analysis revealed that Nigeria's public policy had a significant impact on stock prices.
Coric et al. (2015)	Croatia	2004-2012	VAR	The observation concluded that monetary and fiscal policies complemented each other and had a positive impact on economic growth.
Grazhevska & Virchenko (2014)	Ukraine	2002-2012	Comparative Analysis	The results indicated that the Ukrainian government demanded an improvement in fiscal policy to spur business and economic progress.
Asongu & Jellal (2014)	53 African countries	1996-2010	2SLS	The outcome showed that corruption rose due to government spending but decreased due to investment and tax revenue.
Memon & Ghumro (2014)	Pakistan	1972-2007	VAR	Results showed fiscal policy shifted the business cycle, while monetary policy stabilized the economy.
Melina & Villa (2014)	United State	1954-2007	SVAR and DSGE	The observation suggested that fiscal policy could open up access to loans, leading to economic progress.
Cyrus (2014)	Kenya	1997-2010	VAR	The analysis showed that fiscal policy was more effective than monetary policy in contributing to Kenya's economic growth.
Oseni & Onakoya (2013)	Nigeria	1980-2010	SVAR	The fiscal policy shocks hurt the current balance and interest rate but had a positive effect on output and exchange rate.
Gnip (2013)	Croatia	1995-2011	VAR	The study examined that government spending had a positive impact on economic growth while tax revenue shocks had a negative impact.
Ilegbinosa (2013)	Nigeria	1970-2009	OLS	The study findings showed that public expenditure had a positive impact, while tax revenue did not.
Aremo et al. (2012)	Nigeria	1980-2009	SVAR	The data evaluated that oil prices had a significant impact on GDP.
Tahir & Tahir (2012)	Pakistan	1976-2011	VAR	The authors analyzed that the structural primary balance had a positive and significant impact on GDP, while the output gap had a negative impact.
Medee & Nenbee (2011)	Nigeria	1970-2009	VAR & Error Correlation	The observation showed that FDGE had a short-term negative impact on GDP, while CIF had a positive effect. TRR affected GDP in both the short and long term.
Baum & Koester (2011)	Germany	1976-2009	VAR & OLS	The outcome concluded that fiscal policy was more efficient in the business cycle period.
Baxa (2010)	Czech	1998-2009	VAR	The findings suggested that the effect of public spending was positive and public revenue was negative.

Ponomarenko & Vlasov (2010)	Russia	2008-2010	SVAR	The outcome described that during the crisis Russian government policy had a positive impact on economic output.
Bilbiie et al. (2008)	US	1983-2004	DSGE	The study showed that fiscal shocks had a stronger effect on the economy and monetary policy positively impacted the economy.
Basic (2007)	Serbia	2001-2007	Least Square Regression	The results analyzed that CA was in deficit due to the Serbian government policy.
Arestis & Sawyer (2004)	England	1980s	Empirical Data Method	Results concluded that fiscal policy was more effective, and monetary policy was ineffective in managing the economy.

The studies mention that the VAR methodology is commonly used in developing countries, while only 18 studies focus on developed countries. It is important to note that the results of these studies vary. In these findings according to some authors, we conclude that fiscal policy (government expenditure and taxes) positively affects economic progress, consumption, and investment. In this study, monetary and fiscal policies work together to boost the economy, but we also find some differences because public policy affects the business cycle differently.

MODEL DATA AND METHODOLOGY

In the following models, government spending and Tax revenue are used to examine the impact of fiscal policy transmission on GDP per capita growth, inflation, and unemployment rate.

$$GDPG = f(GS, TAX) \quad (1)$$

$$INF = f(GS, TAX) \quad (2)$$

$$UR = f(GS, TAX) \quad (3)$$

Where:

GS=Government spending

GDPG=Gross domestic per capita growth

TAX=Tax revenue

INF=Inflation

UR=Unemployment rate

In these models, we describe GDP per capita growth, inflation, and unemployment rate as dependent variables while government spending and tax revenue are used as independent variables.

Table 2: Variables, Description, Unit Measurement and Sources of Data

Variables	Description	Unit of Measurement	Data Source
GDPG	GDP per capita growth	(annual %)	WDI
GS	Government spending	(% of GDP)	
TAX	Tax revenue	(% of GDP)	
INF	Inflation rate	(annual %)	
UR	Unemployment rate	(% of total labor force) (modeled ILO estimate)	

In this study, we used time series data which are collected from the Pakistan economy survey and World Development Indicators from 1972 to 2023. We have used the vector autoregression (VAR) model to estimate the results. We have used the impulse response function and variance decomposition with Cholesky adjustment. The important variables used in this study are the following: Tax revenue (TAX), Government spending (GS), Gross domestic product per capita growth (GDPG), Unemployment rate (UR) and Inflation (INF). In this section, we describe the econometric techniques which are the VAR model, ADF Unit root test, Impulse response, and Variance decomposition function.

The Vector Autoregression model (Sims, 1980) estimates the relationship between the variables in different time series. In this study, the most important thing is to understand how to manage the economy. Fiscal policy is more important than monetary policy to control the overall economy because when the rate of interest is changing, it has no significant effect on GDP growth. On the other hand, fiscal policy is more effective because of the influence of government spending and taxes to promote the GDP level. In Pakistan, most studies on fiscal policy transmission mechanisms and in this is use annual data which is collected by World Development Indicators (WDI). In Pakistan, the data is annually collected because, in the annual data, we know the accurate trend of the economy and national income data is accumulating annually. The VAR model is used to remove econometric problems and with the help of this find the one variable impact on the other variable that influences the economy. The accuracy of the analysis is reduced. The reason is that in VAR model and in annual data have more parameters, but the data points are reduced. The VAR model helps understand fiscal policy (Ahmad et al, 2016).

In the VAR model, we use the Impulse response and variance decomposition function. To understand the variables' fluctuation after giving the impulse response we apply these impulse response shocks. The variance decomposition applies to analyze the variations between the variables that cause innovation in variables (Hsing & Hsieh, 2004).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Descriptive statistics of all variables GDP per capita growth, general government final consumption expenditure, tax revenue, Unemployment, and inflation are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables (1972-2023)

	GDPG	GS	TAX	UR	INF
Mean	4.69	4.88	11.01	5.53	10.29
Median	4.41	5.66	11.04	5.45	9.64
Maximum	10.22	31.07	37.05	8.80	25.44
Minimum	0.81	-15.03	1.87	2.10	2.46
Std. Dev.	2.01	8.69	4.64	2.12	5.20
Skewness	0.38	0.24	3.46	-0.03	1.41
Kurtosis	2.92	3.50	21.06	1.53	4.72
Jarque-Bera	1.27	1.05	810.87	4.68	23.67
Probability	0.53	0.59	0.00	0.10	0.00
Observation	52	52	52	52	52

We have used time series data from 1972 to 2023. The average mean value of GDPG is 4.69 % and the median value is 4.41% both represent the central tendency of GDPG. In this 0.81 shows the minimum and 10.22 shows the maximum value of GDPG. The value of SD is 2.01, which represents the moderate variability in GDPG. The skewness value shown in Table 3 is 0.38 which is greater than zero. It shows the GDPG data has been positively skewed. The coefficient of kurtosis is 2.92 which means that the numerical value is less than 3. This indicates that the dispersion is platykurtic. J.B statistic of GDPG is 1.27 and p-value is 0.53 which is greater than 0.10. The null hypothesis is not rejected which shows that distribution is normally distributed.

The average mean value of government spending (GS) is 4.88% which shows a moderate growth rate, and the median value is 5.66%. The value of median and mode indicates the central tendency of GS. The maximum and minimum values of GS are 31.07 and -15.03. The standard deviation is 8.09 which shows the moderate variability in government spending. The maximum government spending is 31.09 and the minimum is -15.03, the negative sign shows that government spending is declining in growth. The standard deviation is 8.69 which shows high variability. The GS skewness is 0.24, which means the numerical value is greater than zero which shows that skewness is positive, and the coefficient of kurtosis is 3.50 which indicates the numerical value is greater than 3 this is called leptokurtic dispersion. Jarque-Bera of government spending is 1.05 and the p-value is 0.59, which indicates that we do not reject the null hypothesis means that data is normally distributed.

The average mean value of the tax is 11.01% and the median is 11.04% which is extremely close to the mean. The maximum value of the tax is 37.05% which shows a high tax rate, and the minimum value of tax is 1.87%. In Table 3, the value of Std.dev is 4.64 which means that moderate variability in tax exists. In this data, the skewness of tax is 3.46 which is greater than 0, which means that this skewed is longer on the right side and this shows that the skewed is positive. The coefficient of kurtosis is 21.06 which indicates the leptokurtic distribution because its value is greater than 3 which shows the high peak. The J.B statistic value is 810.87 and the probability value is

0.00 which is less than 0.10, which shows the null hypothesis of normality is rejected means that this does not follow the normal distribution. The data is non-normally distributed.

The average value of UR is 5.53% and the median UR is 5.45% which is close to the mean value showing the data is symmetric. The range of UR is 2.10 to 8.80 percent. The minimum value of unemployment is 2.10%, which shows that the unemployment level is low, and the maximum value of unemployment is 8.80 which means that unemployment is high. The Std.dev is 2.12 which indicates the moderate variability in data. The UR skewness is negatively skewed because its value is -0.03. In the skewness, the positive or negative sign shows the direction of skewness. The value of UR skewness is less than 0. This shows that the distribution is symmetrical distribution, and the kurtosis value is 1.53 which indicates the numerical value is less than 3. This is known as platykurtic distribution. It indicates that the distribution is low peaked means that flatter than the normal distribution. The J.B test statics of UR are 4.68 and the P value is 0.10, which indicates that data does not reject the null hypothesis which shows that data distribution is normally distributed.

The average mean value of INF is 10.29% which indicates the inflation level is high. The median of INF is 9.64%. The minimum and maximum value of inflation is respectively 2.46% and 25.44%. The minimum value of inflation indicates low inflation, and the maximum value indicates high inflation. The value of the standard deviation is 5.20, which shows the moderate variability in INF which is high. The coefficient of skewness is 1.41 which is greater than 0. We say that this skew is positively skewed means that the tail is longer on the right side. The kurtosis of INF is 4.72 which indicates that the numerical value is greater than 3 which is known as leptokurtic distribution. The test statistics used J.B statistics, its value is 23.67 and the p-value is 0.00 which is less than 0.10 it shows that the null hypothesis of normality is rejected. It indicates that data is non-normally distributed.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis of Key Variables (1972-2023)

Correlation	GDPG	GS	INF	TAX	UR
GDPG	1.00				
GS	0.21	1.00			
INF	-0.15	-0.07	1.00		
TAX	-0.09	0.14	-0.14	1.00	
UR	-0.29	-0.18	-0.05	-0.28	1.00

A correlation matrix is employed to analyze the relationship between variables. In Table 4, INF, TAX, and UR weekly negatively correlated with GDPG and GS has week positive correlation with GDPG. The INF and UR show a weak negative correlation with GS and TAX has a positive weak correlation with the GS. TAX and UR have negatively correlated with INF. In these respectively -0.14 and -0.05, negative signs indicate the direction and value show the strength of relation. The UR has a weak negative correlation with TAX.

UNIT ROOT ANALYSIS

We have used the ADF test to find the unit root and apply the ADF test on the level to check that variables are stationary or not stationary in time series data. Table 5 gives the results of the ADF test.

Table 5: ADF Unit Root Test Results

Variables	None	Lags	Intercept	Lags	Intercept & Trends	Lags	Conclusion
GDPG	-1.5465 (0.1135)	0	-5.27118 (0.0001)	0	-6.1045 (0.0000)	0	I (0)
GS	-3.4210 (0.0010)	1	-3.4210 (0.0000)	0	-9.1569 (0.0000)	0	I (0)
INF	-1.5729 (0.1079)	2	-5.4745 (0.0000)	0	-5.4649 (0.0002)	0	I (0)
TAX	-3.8362 (0.0003)	0	-9.7121 (0.0000)	0	-9.1782 (0.0000)	0	I (0)
UR	0.841813 (0.8896)	0	-1.2147 (0.1633)	0	-2.9710 (0.1502)	0	I (1)

Table 5 shows that the GDPG variables are stationary at intercept and intercept & trend here both lags are 0 but the GDPG is not stationary at none because the probability value is greater than 0.10 and this also lag value is

zero. The GS is stationary significant with none, and this lag value is 1 but the GS variable has no unit root which means stationary significance at intercept, intercept & trend and both lag values are 0. The INF is not stationary at none with lag 2 and INF is stationary at intercept, intercept & trend and both lag values are 0. The variable TAX series has no unit root at none, intercept, and intercept & trend, and all lags are 0 but the UR is not stationary at none, intercept and intercept & trend and all lags are 0. Overall, ADF unit root tests conclude that there is a mixed order of integration.

RESULTS OF OPTIMAL LAG SELECTION

Table 6 uses the optimal lag for the selection. AIC, SC, and HQ are the lag selection criteria. In this result, we find that the optimal lag is one because in lag 1 the LR, FPE, AIC, SC, and HQ values are low as compared to other lags.

Table 6: VAR, Lag Order Selection Criteria: endogenous variables (GDPG, TAX, INF &UR)

Lag	Log L	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-584.36	NA	53641.92	25.079	25.276	25.153
1	-481.14	180.09*	1935.776*	21.750*	22.931*	22.195*
2	-457.85	35.67	2161.177	21.823	23.988	22.638
3	-445.96	15.68	4161.226	22.381	25.530	23.566
4	-424.93	23.26	6003.194	22.550	26.683	24.105
5	-399.94	22.33	8595.909	22.550	27.668	24.476

IMPULSE RESPONSE FUNCTION ANALYSIS

Through the Impulse response function, we observe the shock of one variable on the other variables. With the Cholesky decomposition in this, we analyze the VAR model. In the impulse response, the solid line is the baseline. On this baseline, we observed the variation from one variable to another variable with the help of impulse response. In this, we estimate the effect over time. We show the impulse response on GS and TAX.

Figure 1: Impulse Response Function to Government Spending Shocks (Response to Cholesky One S.D. (df adjusted) innovations $\pm 2 S. E.$)

IRF FOR GOVERNMENT SPENDING SHOCKS

Figure 1 shows that government spending shock is positive in gross domestic product growth (GDPG). This reveals a clear infusion of demand in the economy, stabilizing economic activity. Initially, Government spending impulse caused inflation to rise through an increase in aggregate demand. However, the influence stabilizes steadily, simulating the transient nature of demand-driven inflationary pressures. A reduction in the unemployment rate is

noticed in response to increased government spending, underscoring the function of fiscal incentives in job creation. The effects on GDPG and inflation reduce over the periods, suggesting the diminishing effectiveness of the spending shock. This could be through the replacement effects or supply-side limitations. The results suggested the short-term impacts of government spending as an instrument for economic growth and employment generation. However, long-term dependence on spending needs a careful analysis of fiscal sustainability.

IRF FOR TAX REVENUE SHOCKS

When we give one SD positive Shock in tax revenue typically generates a negative influence, reflected in a decrease in initial GDP growth. As a result, decreases the disposable income and total demand. Tax innovations frequently reduced inflation and reduced the corresponding spending power among businesses and consumers. Furthermore, effects on the unemployment are integrated. Higher taxes might influence economic activity and increase the unemployment rate, the level changes based on the structure of the taxation system and redistributive influences. The economy reveals that adjusting to tax revenue shocks gradually, with GDPG and inflation stabilizing after the initial periods of instability. Tax policies must be adjusted to prevent extreme negative effects on growth and employment. The use of taxation plans can help to control government spending without affecting economic growth.

Moreover, the results show that government spending shocks have a more positive impact on GDP growth as compared to tax shocks. While both government spending and tax shocks present a decreasing influence over time, tax shocks frequently take longer time to stabilize economic growth through their broader influence on total demand and supply. In the short run government spending is inflationary, whereas tax revenue impulse applies deflationary pressure. Government spending decreases the unemployment rate, whereas tax revenue shocks can have different impacts based on economic stability.

Figure 2: Impulse Response Function to Taxes (Response to Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) innovations $\pm 2 S. E.$)

VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION (VD) ANALYSIS

In Table 7 the variance decomposition (VD) evaluates and provides a complete understanding of how innovations to different variables affect their own variances and the variances of others over time. This section describes the involvements of tax revenue (TAX), government spending (GS), inflation (INF), GDP growth (GDPG), and the unemployment rate (UR) to each other and forecasts the error variances.

For GDP growth (GDPG), explaining 98.07% of its variance in the short run period (own shock). In the long run, this effect decreases partially to 73.65% and reveals a strong determination in GDP growth. Inflation (INF) accounts for 19.08% of GDPG variance over the tenth period, illustrating its increasing function in economic activity. Government spending (GS) has a constrained but increasing effect on GDPG, rising to 2.34% over the tenth period. Tax revenue (TAX) and the unemployment rate (UR) have a limited impact on GDPG variance, showing another role in running economic stability in the short-term and medium-term.

Table 7: Variance Decomposition Function of Endogenous Variables

Period	S.E.	GS	GDPG	INF	TAX	UR
Variance Decomposition of GDPG						
1	1.63	1.92	98.07	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	1.75	1.77	88.75	6.60	1.30	1.55
3	1.96	1.47	76.09	19.62	1.30	1.49
4	1.99	2.16	74.80	20.14	1.39	1.49
5	2.02	2.18	74.54	19.76	1.65	1.83
6	2.04	2.34	74.18	19.45	1.97	2.04
7	2.06	2.33	73.84	19.32	2.15	2.34
8	2.07	2.36	73.76	19.16	2.18	2.52
9	2.08	2.35	73.73	19.08	2.18	2.64
10	2.09	2.34	73.65	19.08	2.16	2.74
Variance Decomposition of GS						
Period	S.E.	GS	GDPG	INF	TAX	UR
1	7.37	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	8.66	86.25	10.29	2.42	0.83	0.19
3	9.12	81.01	14.26	2.20	1.27	1.24
4	9.28	78.99	13.78	4.22	1.78	1.20
5	9.35	78.22	14.07	4.69	1.81	1.19
6	9.35	78.18	14.07	4.69	1.84	1.19
7	9.36	78.06	14.17	4.69	1.86	1.20
8	9.36	78.05	14.17	4.69	1.87	1.20
9	9.36	78.02	14.19	4.70	1.87	1.21
10	9.36	78.01	14.20	4.70	1.87	1.21
Variance Decomposition of TAX						
Period	S.E.	GS	GDPG	INF	TAX	UR
1	0.98	2.98	5.41	9.75	81.84	0.00
2	1.48	2.89	2.59	9.59	84.65	0.25
3	1.71	2.69	2.34	12.90	81.81	0.24
4	1.79	2.47	2.18	16.22	78.68	0.44
5	1.80	2.61	2.29	16.64	77.29	1.15
6	1.83	2.69	3.09	16.12	75.97	2.10
7	1.87	2.77	4.26	15.58	74.57	2.80
8	1.90	2.79	5.42	15.16	73.39	3.21
9	1.92	2.79	6.43	14.91	72.45	3.40
10	1.93	2.78	7.14	14.86	71.72	3.47
Variance Decomposition of UR						
Period	S.E.	GS	GDPG	INF	TAX	UR
1	0.65	1.72	4.72	4.12	2.55	86.86
2	0.91	3.36	19.24	2.83	1.74	72.82
3	1.12	3.01	34.35	2.24	1.14	59.24
4	1.31	2.67	42.33	4.24	0.90	49.84
5	1.47	2.69	46.00	7.20	0.77	43.32

6	1.61	2.62	48.45	9.08	0.71	39.12
7	1.72	2.55	50.29	10.12	0.71	36.31
8	1.81	2.51	51.49	10.83	0.77	34.37
9	1.89	2.50	52.36	11.31	0.84	32.97
10	1.96	2.49	53.07	11.59	0.91	31.91
Variance Decomposition of INF						
Period	S.E.	GS	GDPG	INF	TAX	UR
1	4.60	0.05	1.37	98.56	0.00	0.00
2	4.84	5.60	2.13	90.47	0.61	1.16
3	4.98	9.15	3.14	85.76	0.75	1.18
4	5.01	9.47	3.16	84.61	1.54	1.19
5	5.03	9.39	3.20	83.92	2.22	1.25
6	5.05	9.38	3.28	83.60	2.45	1.26
7	5.06	9.36	3.28	83.56	2.52	1.26
8	5.06	9.36	3.28	83.55	2.52	1.26
9	5.06	9.36	3.28	83.52	2.54	1.27
10	5.06	9.36	3.28	83.48	2.58	1.27

Government spending (GS) is described by its past performance with a big impact of 100% from the past values, reducing to 78.01% in the long-run period. GDPG influences the GS significantly with its increasing to 14.20% over time, showing a spiral where economic presentation affects the fiscal conclusion. Inflation plays an important role in supporting 4.69% in the long-run period, via its influence on the cost of government expenditures. Tax revenue (TAX) and unemployment (UR) negatively to GS variance, highlighting the restricted clear interactions in fiscal policy conclusions.

In the short run, tax revenue (TAX) has a strong influence and explains 81.84% of its innovations and decreases to 71.72% in the long-run period. Inflation increases and supports 14.86% to TAX variance in the long run, likely showing its influence on the tax base. GDP growth (GDPG) contributes strongly influence contributing at 7.14%, while government spending (GS) has a minor effect. The unemployment rate (UR) reveals the restricted impact, supporting 3.47% in the long-run period, showing the weaker relationship between labor market conditions and tax revenue performance.

The unemployment rate (UR) shocked 86.86% in the short run and reduced to 31.91% in the long-run period. GDP growth (GDPG) is an important variable that explains 53.07% of UR shocks in the long run, highlighting the huge link between economic growth and employment. Inflation (INF) accounts for 11.59% of UR impulse, persistent with Phillips curve changes, where price adjustments affect the labor market conditions. Government spending (GS) and tax revenue (TAX) have a limited contribution, showing that fiscal policy gradually affects unemployment implicitly.

Inflation (INF) is mostly self-reliant, with its own shock explained by 98.56% in the short run and reduced to 83.48% in the long run. Government spending (GS) and GDP growth (GDPG) slightly affect inflation and its variance of 9.36% and 3.28% respectively in the long run. Tax revenue (TAX) shows the nominal influence and supports 2.58%, while the unemployment rate (UR) has a minor impact on the inflation impulse.

In summary, the VD results show that every variable is initially controlled by its own shocks. While external impacts are becoming more distinct over time. GDP growth plays an important function in affecting the other variables. Inflation's increasing effect on GDP growth and fiscal components stimulates its universal effects on economic growth. Tax revenue presents constraints and links with other variables, highlighting its autonomous nature. These observations are vital for policymakers aiming to design effective fiscal policies that link the interdependence between economic growth, labor markets, inflation, and fiscal components.

CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the fiscal policy transmission mechanism in Pakistan from 1972 to 2023. The Impulse Response Function (IRF) and Variance Decomposition (VD) analyses collectively demonstrate the dynamic interactions between government spending, tax revenue, GDP growth, inflation, and unemployment. The IRF analysis reveals that government spending shocks have a positive short-term impact on GDP growth and employment while exerting inflationary pressure, with effects tapering off overtime suggesting

short-term fiscal stimulus is effective but may not be sustainable long-term. In contrast, tax revenue shocks generally have a contractionary effect, reducing GDP growth and increasing unemployment, although their effects stabilize slowly. Particularly, tax shocks exert deflationary pressures, whereas spending shocks are inflationary. The VD results support these findings, showing that GDP growth is primarily self-determined but increasingly influenced by inflation and government spending overtime. Similarly, government spending is mainly driven by its past values, with rising contributions from GDP growth and inflation, while tax revenue is most influenced by its own innovations and inflation. Unemployment is significantly affected by GDP growth in the long run, reinforcing the role of economic activity in labor market outcomes. In a nutshell, fiscal tools like spending and taxation have asymmetric and time-sensitive effects on macroeconomic stability, underlining the need for careful policy calibration.

The results suggest different important policy recommendations for analyzing fiscal and macroeconomic management. Primary observations are the difficult role of stable economic growth (GDPG) in affecting the other variables, likely unemployment rate and government spending. To attain this, policymakers should focus on increasing productivity via investments in infrastructure, technology, and human capital. Enhancing the private sector development and improved stable and predictable fiscal and policies are also important for attracting investments and enhancing consumer confidence.

Inflation (INF) is explained as an important objective, given its universal effects on government spending, GDP growth, and tax revenues. Effective inflation control can be attained by stabilizing the monetary policy specifications to make the inflation within objective ranges. Policymakers should present supply-side restrictions, particularly in vital sectors like food, energy and reduced cost-push inflation. Planned fiscal and monetary policies are important to balance demand pressures and stable fiscal sustainability.

Government spending (GS) has a determinable but constrained influence on GDP growth and unemployment rate, suggesting the requirement for more objective fiscal interventions. Policymakers should value increasing the productivity expenditures in healthcare, education, and infrastructure to raise long-term economic advantages. Monetary and evaluating public spending effectiveness is important to increase the fiscal resources are effectively utilized. Extreme reliance on financed deficit spending should be prevented to avoid inflationary pressures and increase fiscal health.

Tax revenue (TAX) has a limited impact on GDP growth but is crucially influenced by the inflation rate and unemployment rate. Reforming tax policies to expand the tax base and improve compliance can increase a steady revenue stream without extreme rate increases. Policymakers should consider implementing progressive taxation to reduce the adverse impacts on total demand while stabilizing social equity. Linking the tax policies with growing purposes is important to improve they do not restrain business activity

Unemployment (UR) is influenced by GDP growth, highlighting the requirement for labor market policies that contribute to job creation. Policymakers should make the skill development programs linked with industry requirements to decrease structural unemployment. Targeted observations for labor-intensive sectors, like manufacturing, agriculture, and services, can help to create jobs. Implementing social safety nets and unemployment insurance programs can offer support during the economic crisis.

The relationship between tax revenues, government spending, and inflation underscores the significance of fiscal and monetary policy coordination. Fiscal policies should be countercyclical, boarding during crisis and consolidating during increasing periods to stabilize the economy. Clear relationships between fiscal and monetary authorities can increase policy credibility and effectiveness. Establishing robust early warning systems and plans to address economic shocks is also important for policy adaptability.

In conclusion, these policy recommendations highlight a balanced approach to fiscal and macroeconomic management. By prioritizing inflation control, sustained growth, tax reforms targeted spending, and fostering labor market resilience and policy coordination, policymakers can increase economic stability and development. Continuous analysis and adaptation of policies in reply to variations in economic conditions will further enhance their effectiveness.

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